

benzene was then distilled off and the resulting solid washed with aqueous 10% sodium carbonate solution and finally recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity : Antibacterial activity of all the synthesised compounds, 2a-k and 3a-k except 2e, m and 3l were screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Sarcina lutea* by the agar-plate-diffusion technique¹⁵. The standard antibacterial drug used was tetracycline. A standard 5 mm diameter sterilised filter paper disc impregnated with the compound (1 mg ml⁻¹ of acetone) was placed on an agar-plate seeded with test organism. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°. The zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc was observed. The screening results are given in Table 2, indicated that all the compounds exhibited antibacterial activities less than the standard used. The antibacterial activities of azomethines 2a-k are comparable to their cyclised products thiazolidinones 3a-k. No structure-activity relationship could be established, since the degree of inhibition produced by azomethines and thiazolidines were fairly constant.

Fungicidal activity : All the compounds (2a-k and 2a-k) were screened for fungicidal activity on *Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus niger* at different dilutions. The results are summarised in Table 2. The fungicidal screening was carried out by determining the percentage inhibition of colonial growth in comparison to the growth in control¹⁶. All solutions were prepared in acetone and the medium in the treated plates was potato dextrose agar culture medium and the incubation time was 96 h at 28 ± 1°. From Table 2 it is evident that the compounds 2 and 3 are capable of inhibiting fungal growth to a considerable extent both at high and low dilutions.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Saxena, Head, Chemistry Department, for facilities, and to Mr. V. K. Chaubey, Department of Botany, for the fungicidal screening.

References

- O. KIYOSHI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 33180
- S. BHADUR, A. K. GOEL and R. S. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1163.
- A. K. SENGUPTA and M. GOYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 766.
- D. WERNER, B. WOLFGANG, H. INGEBORG, S. HANDS and B. WILHELM, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 87969.
- W. HANS, D. GUENTER and H. PAUL, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 136680
- P. C. JOHNSON, C. J. WESLEY and W. J. HOWARD, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **87**, 53298.
- V. V. BOSSCHE, F. ROCHETIE and C. HORIG, *Adv. Pharmacol. Chemother.*, 1962, **19**, 67.
- S. SHARMA and S. ABUZAR, *Prog. Drug. Res.*, 1983, **27**, 85.
- M. K. RAUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2427.
- S. V. PATEL, N. Y. NAGAR and G. B. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 304.
- H. D. TROUTMANN and M. M. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3436.

- A. R. SURREY and R. A. CUTLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **76**, 578.
- R. K. SAXENA and P. KANT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 722.
- A. BLOOM and A. R. DAY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, **4**, 16.
- R. S. VERMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, **13**, 45.
- J. G. HORSPALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, **11**, 357.

Chemical Constituents of *Citrullus colocynthis*

S. P. GARG* and UPMA GUPTA

Desert Plant Analysis Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 1 December 1986, revised 11 May 1987,
accepted 6 July 1987

FRUITS of *Citrullus colocynthis*, a medicinal plant of desert region¹⁻⁴, were collected from different areas of Jodhpur district for the present study. The fruit coat was initially separated from the pulp. Both fruit coat and the pulp were extracted separately in soxhlet with benzene and ethyl acetate successively. The extracts were distilled and the gummy residues chromatographed over silica gel in separate columns. Elution of the benzene extract of the fruit coat with petrol-benzene (85 : 15) gave a compound, which on crystallisation from hot acetone gave a pure compound (A). m.p. 69°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 920, 2 830, 1 472, 1 385, 1 305, 735 and 720 cm⁻¹; δ 0.95 and 1.2. It was found identical with hentriacontane (m.m.p. and ir)^{5,6}. Elution of the benzene extract of fruit pulp with petrol-benzene (80 : 20) also furnished the same compound (A), which was found identical with hentriacontane (m.m.p. and ir).

The chromatogram on further elution with benzene-methanol (90 : 10 and 80 : 20) yielded two compounds (C and D), which were separated with plc. The compound C was crystallised with methanol, m.p. 82-83°, M^+ 514 (Found : C, 69.76 ; H, 8.13. C₃₀H₄₂O₇ requires : C, 70.03 ; H, 7.78%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400, 1 686, 1 660, 1 620, 1 413, 1 248, 1 141, 1 080, 985 and 870 cm⁻¹ ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (EtOH) 230 (4.2) and 270 nm (2.2). It was found identical with elateridine in its reactions, ir and uv, but its m.p. (82-3°) was much lower than that reported (134-35°) for elateridine.

Compound D was crystallised to furnish a solid, m.p. 116°, M^+ 400 (Found : C, 71.87 ; H, 8.12. C₂₄H₃₂O₅ requires : C, 72.00 ; H, 8.03%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400, 3 350, 1 715, 1 690, 1 660, 1 587, 1 385, 1 040, 980 and 970 cm⁻¹ ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (EtOH) 240 (3.5) and 270 (1.6) ; δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 5.0 (1H, m), 2.22 (3H, s), 0.9-1.2 (15 H). Acetylation with Py-Ac₂O (at room temperature) gave monoacetate, m.p. 140°, M^+ 442 (Found : C, 70.54 ; H, 7.72 ; CH₃CO, 9.20. C₂₆H₃₄O₆ requires : C, 70.58 ; H, 7.69 ; CH₃CO (1 acetyl group), 9.72%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 350, 1 740, 1 720, 1 690, 1 660, 1 589.

* 55 Bhagat-ki-kothi Extension Scheme, Jodhpur-342 003.

1 390, 1 248, 1 140, 1 080, 970 and 870 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 240 (3.7) and 295 (2.2); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 4.9 (1H), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.1 (3H) and 0.9–1.2 (15 H). Acetylation with Ac_2O –sodium acetate (on reflux) gave the diacetate, m.p. 180° (lit.⁷ 180–82°); M^+ 484 (Found: C, 69.34; H, 7.70; CH_3CO , 17.25. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 69.42; H, 7.43; CH_3CO (2 acetyl groups), 17.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 740, 1 720, 1 690, 1 660, 1 590, 1 390, 1 170, 980 and 870 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 240 (3.9) and 320 (1.8); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 4.9 (1H), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.1 (6H), 0.9–1.3 (15H). It was thus characterised as hexanor-cucurbitacin I.

Further elution of chromatogram with benzene–methanol (70 : 30) yielded a solid E, m.p. 140–42°, M^+ 442 (Found: C, 70.61; H, 7.64; CH_3CO , 10.11. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_6$ requires: C, 70.58; H, 7.69; CH_3CO (1 acetyl group), 10.18%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 3 350, 1 740, 1 715, 1 690, 1 660, 1 587, 1 385, 1 040, 980 and 970; λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 240 (3.5) and 295 (1.6); δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 5.0 (1H, m), 2.4 (3H, s), 2.22 (3H, s) and 0.9–1.35 (15 H). It was found identical with monoacetate of D and 16-*O*-acetylhexanor-cucurbitacin I (m.m.p., m.p., ir, uv, nmr).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor R. C. Kapoor, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur, for facilities and encouragement and to the University of Jodhpur, for awarding a Fellowship to one of them (U. G.).

References

1. M. M. BHANDARI, "Flora of the Indian Desert", Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur, 1978, p. 161.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medical Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956.
3. G. V. SATYAVATI, M. K. RAINA and M. SHARMA, "Medicinal Plants of India", I. C. M. R., New Delhi, 1976, Vol. 1.
4. V. ERSPAMER and A. PAOLINO, *Experientia*, 1946, 2, 455.
5. R. R. AGARWAL and S. DUTT, *Curr. Sci.*, 1934, 3, 250.
6. B. HAMILTON and W. O. KERMAK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 5051.
7. M. M. RAO, H. MERSHULAM and D. LAVIC, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 2552.

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Nickel with Diphenylcarbazone in Presence of Pyridine

KABITA SARMAH and H. K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Gauhati University,
Guwahati-781 014

Manuscript received 19 November 1986, revised 18 May 1987,
accepted 6 July 1987

DIPHENYLCARBAZONE has long been known as a reagent for the detection and determination of a number of metals^{1–3}. It forms chelate complexes with many heavy metals^{4,5}. Nickel(II)

forms a pink coloured 1 : 2 complex⁶ with it, but the colour of the complex fades rather rapidly. In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of pyridine, nickel(II) forms with diphenylcarbazone a purple coloured complex which is extractable into methyl isobutyl ketone. When pyridine is replaced by other heterocyclic bases like picolines and collidine, the sensitivity of the colour reaction is much less. Thus, it is found that diphenylcarbazone and pyridine make a suitable ligand pair for the determination of nickel(II) spectrophotometrically. This forms the basis of the present method which has proved to be very simple and sensitive.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used for absorbance measurements. pH values were determined with a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

A stock solution of nickel was prepared from $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) in distilled water and standardised gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime reagent⁶. Solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 0.2% solution of diphenylcarbazone (B.D.H.) in absolute alcohol and a 5% pyridine solution in distilled water were employed as reagents. Solutions of 0.2 *M* boric acid, 0.2 *M* sodium hydroxide and 0.2 *M* potassium chloride were prepared to constitute the required buffer. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the test solution containing 0.5 to 10 μg of nickel, 5% pyridine (2 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml) were added and the total volume was made upto 10 ml so that pH of the aqueous phase maintained around 9.0. To it 0.2% diphenylcarbazone solution (1 ml) and then MIBK (10 ml) were added and the resulting mixture was shaken for 5 min in a separatory funnel. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 530 nm against the reagent blank. The nickel content in unknown solutions was computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The nickel(II)–diphenylcarbazone–pyridine complex system exhibits maximum absorbance at 530 nm when measured against the reagent blank and obeys Beer's law over the range 0.05–1 ppm of Ni^{II} . The optimum concentration range is found to be 0.1–1 ppm of Ni^{II} . The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.000 61 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity $9.62 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 530 nm.

The results of extraction studies of nickel–diphenylcarbazone–pyridine system show that